

Micro- and Nanostructured Carbon Electrodes for Capacitive Energy Storage

Students from NTU-RPI-DTU Innovation workshop

ABSTRACT

At last years innovation workshop, several projects looked into supercapacitor structures, and this project will follow up in this, with emphasis on comparing capacitive performance of bulk electrodes with those of lithographically defined structures such as interdigitated electrodes. You should consider different ways of creating the electrodes such as structures made of grapheme or from pyrolysed polymers. In this project you should perform a literature review on the methods used for creating supercapacitors and propose possible ways to improve the current state of art based on simple test experiments.